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HIPPARCOS reductions for multiple stars, XV
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This note is a short status report for the '1-year' DS-reductions. The 'Case History Files' for 10246 known doubles and 11755 suspected non-singles have now been successfully derived. The first comparisons with sphere solution data indicate that any remaining systematic errors are below the 1 mas-level.

1. CHF-derivation

The CHF-generation uses some 10 different programs in a complex chain (cf. NDAC/LO/132). This chain was successfully run through in May, giving a set of CHF:s that will be used for a large series of solution-experiments. The main changes from last year's provisional runs concerns the photometric calibrations. Apart from improved calibration-coefficients from RGO, a detailed background-model has also been incorporated. This is again done at RGO, and the background-level (for the IDT-counts) is given about once per 5 frames. Because the data come from a model (calibrated from star-mapper data), they are reasonably smooth over much longer stretches, and I have remodelled the variation as a set of about 250 linear segments per (7-8 hour) set. These new data are saved in the general 'calibration'-file, which has thus been suitably enlarged.

The actual CHF-derivation ran smoothly, but for lack of disc-space, a large number of temporary saves and reloads from magnetic tape were necessary. During these operations, data from three (out of 812) sets were lost, but this should have a very limited influence on the results for most stars. The final output is one 48Mb file with 'known double' CHF:s, one 48Mb file with 'suspected non-single' CHF:s, and a smaller (2.5 Mb) file with CHF:s for known multiples.

The complexity of the CHF-generation process makes it very important to try to verify its correctness. The only data available with sufficient accuracy are the sphere solution results for nominally single stars. These are derived from a very different reduction path (including the 'detour' through the great-circle reductions), and agreement for positions and parallaxes derived in the sphere solution and in the DS-reductions is strong evidence for the correctness of both. The comparisons so far made are described below.

2. Sphere solution comparisons for single stars

With a rather liberal flagging of suspected non-singles, a large fraction of the selected objects will indeed be single. The SEEKDBL program seeks for new doubles, but it gives also positions and parallaxes for those objects where no double star model seems to fit. These single star data may now be compared with the output from the sphere solution, and ideally, any deviations should be within the computed mean errors. Such a comparison was done a year ago with the provisional data, and this verified the CHF-derivation to within some 10 mas. The present

comparison is much more stringent, because the mean errors are now mostly below 3 mas, and a much larger number of stars may be compared.

I have so far run SEEKDBL for IC-numbers 1-50 000, without any parameter optimizations. These solutions gave single-star positions and parallaxes for 1303 stars in common with Lennart Lindegren's sphere solution. The agreement is very satisfying, and can be quantified by studying the distributions of $(\Delta\alpha/\sigma)$, $(\Delta\delta/\sigma)$ and $(\Delta\pi/\sigma)$. The means and standard deviations for these normalized distributions are 0.25 (1.27), -0.09 (1.38) and -0.01 (1.15), while a plot of the actual π -differences versus magnitude is shown in Fig 1.

Fig 1. Parallax differences between the DS and sphere solutions plotted versus magnitude.

Fig 2. Differences between the 3,3 (π) covariances calculated in the sphere and in the DS solutions as function of the number of different scan-directions. The line is the rough fit $28 \text{ (mas)}^2/\text{nscan}$.

The σ -values used above are those calculated by Lindegren in the sphere solution. I have compared the full 3x3 covariance-matrices given from SEEKDBL with that from the sphere solution, and there seems to be no systematic differences for the cross-terms. For the diagonal terms, the SEEKDBL covariances are lower, with an interesting dependence on the number of observations. In the CHF-derivation, the

attitudes are assumed to be 'perfect', but in reality there are still appreciable errors due to the imperfect star-positions used in the attitude determination. These errors can be very approximately assumed to give a contribution in the along-scan direction that is 'constant' as long as the scan-angle is reasonably constant. I have thus studied the covariance-differences with respect to a parameter $nscan$ which gives the number of different scan-directions in which an object has been observed. Roughly, as expected from such a model, the covariance-difference (Sph-DS) is inversely proportional to $nscan$. The added covariance per scan is about 13 (mas)^2 in δ , 16 (mas)^2 in α and 28 (mas)^2 in π , which is also quantitatively reasonable. Fig 2 shows the effect in parallax.

3. Sphere solution comparisons for wide doubles

Another important test comparison is for wide doubles where the components have been independently observed. For some of these (not all, because they are by definition avoided in the sphere solution!) there are (disturbed) sphere solution results, and these may be compared with rigorous double-star reductions for the components taken together. Presently, I have data for 272 individual components, and the parallax deviations are plotted in Fig 3 against $\Delta m_e = \Delta m + \Delta m(IFOV)$, where $\Delta m(IFOV)$ is the IFOV attenuation at the component separation. As expected, the parallaxes agree to within a few mas for large Δm_e , while for larger disturbances, the sphere-solution results start to be unreliable. A very similar figure is obtained for the position deviations, except for a possible problem with the 30 points corresponding to secondary components. (For these, there are position-deviations of about $\pm 50 \text{ mas}$ even at $\Delta m_e \sim 5$ which are *not* reflected in the parallax results. This may signal some real error in my STDDBL program which should be investigated further).

Fig 3. Parallax differences between the sphere and DS solutions for components of wide doubles.

4. Photometric variability

I have only started to look at the photometric variations, which do however look a bit larger and more common than I had realized. Fig 4 is a simple plot of standard deviations for the 'DC' magnitudes (as given from the list of b(1)-observations for each star) versus mean magnitude for 4800 'suspected non-single' CHF:s. There

seems to be a natural division between 'normal' observational scatter and 'real' variability at a σ about 0.15, and the large number of variables is at once apparent.

Fig 4. The raw observed standard deviation in total (DC) magnitude for about 4800 'suspected non-single' objects.

In the SEEKDBL solutions, some 8% of the stars can not be fitted to either a single or a double star solution. Part of these problems are certainly due to variability, as seen e.g. by the fact that the *median* magnitude- σ for these objects is about 0.23. The proper modelling of doubles with variable components remains to be done.

5. Conclusion

The CHF-generation for the '1-year' data seems to be well in hand, and work with the actual solution programs can now proceed. Because the 'final' Input Catalogue (IC9) is still not available, the double star selections are based on IC8, but with an added 300 systems from the '2:nd CHARA Catalogue' by McAlister and Hartkopf.

The next major step is now to solve for a large number of known doubles and then compare the results for the relative positions with those derived by FAST. Similar comparisons should be done for new discoveries. (The above runs of SEEKDBL have already given a list of over 2000 new systems, but the parameters determined may not yet be trusted for all of them).